

ANTONYMY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS: FORMAL AND SEMANTIC SIMILARITY AS A CRITERION OF OPPOSITION

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Annotation. The article compares the ideas of phraseological antonyms existing in linguistics. The conditions for the emergence of antonymic relations between phraseological units are specified, the formal signs of antonymic oppositions are identified and systematized. The author's classification of phraseological antonyms is developed on the basis of the type of opposite indicated, the problem of opposition of phraseological and lexical units is analyzed. Comparison of phraseological units of unrelated English and Uzbek languages revealed many common features, from which it follows that antonymy is a universal phenomenon.

Key words: phraseological antonym, antonymic criteria, opposite meanings, semantic structure, differential feature.

INTRODUCTION

This study is a fragment of the analysis of antonymic relations on the basis of phraseological units. The article identifies semantic and formal criteria for the antonymy of phraseological units, presents their classification in accordance with the selected criteria, and confirms that antonymy is a universal phenomenon inherent in natural languages, which is based on mental mechanisms that do not have national-individual or national-peculiar specifics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to the point of view of F. de Saussure, the syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations of its units underlie the structural organization of the language [4, p. 155–156]. As we know, it is most difficult to identify the configuration of

syntagmatics and paradigmatics in vocabulary and phraseology, which is explained by constant replenishment of the lexical composition of the language and the indirectly derivative nature of phrasemics [4; 2].

There is no doubt that antonymy is one of the forms of implementation of paradigmatic relations in the field of phrasemics, along with the variance of the lexical composition of phrasemes, relations of a synonymic nature, particular meanings of polysemantic phrasemes and thematic series formed by common referential relations of phrasemes.

According to A.B. Kunin, phraseological antonyms are phraseological units that have a common semantic component in the presence of polarity of meanings [1, p. 134]. The antonymy of phraseological units is ensured by the homogeneous semantic structure of language units in the presence of opposite components in it, due to which opposition is created in a pair of antonyms.

Semantic homogeneity provides a basis for comparison. Phraseological units fly off the handle - “nazoratdan chiqarmoq” and work one's fingers to the bone - “tinim bilmay ishlamoq” describe actions, but in this case there is no basis for comparison, since the first unit characterizes the mental state of a person, the second - labor activity. At the same time, the opposition of the idioms work one's fingers to the bone - “qattiq ishlamoq” and twiddle one's thumbs - “bekor yurmoq” is justified, since they both convey the attitude to work, characterizing activity and inactivity.

The second criterion of antonymy is the presence of ultimate negation in the semantic structure of the compared language units, which determines the ability of antonyms to express opposite concepts, in contrast to contradictory (opposition) concepts. In other words, the antonymic paradigm combines linguistic units with opposite meanings, in the semantic structure of which there is a common integral feature and a differential feature that expresses the ultimate opposition of meanings.

Phraseologisms enter into antonymic relations when their opposite extends to all elements of meaning: to get into a rut - “iziga tushnoq”, “odatiy hayotga

qaytmoq” and get out of the rut - "izdan chiqmoq”; be in good form - “yaxshi holatda bo’lmoq”; and be in bad form - “yomon holatda bo’lmoq.”

Considering the semantics of phraseological antonyms, G.B. Mardanova notes the influence of semantic symmetry / asymmetry on the degree of opposition of units. Like lexemes, phraseological units denoting opposite signs are at the poles of the scale, and between them there can be a third member that neutralizes the opposition. Depending on the location of the phraseological antonym in relation to the middle link (its proximity or remoteness), additional components that weaken or strengthen its meaning may appear in its meaning, and a pair of antonyms is recognized as symmetrical or asymmetric. The scientist distinguishes three degrees of antonymy of phraseological units: low, medium and high.

The opposition of antonyms with a symmetrical semantic structure is recognized as strong. The opposition, represented by a symmetrical phraseological antonym and an asymmetric phraseological antonym, which has additional, non-coinciding meaning components, is characterized by an average degree of antonymy. A low degree of antonymy is inherent in phraseological units, the opposite meaning components of which are not polar, asymmetric [2, p. 7].

RESULTS

The classification of phraseological antonyms based on the typology of the designated opposite is proposed by E.N. Miller in his work "The nature of lexical and phraseological antonymy" [3, p. 98–102]. Having slightly changed and supplemented it, we propose a classification of phraseological antonyms of the English language:

1) antonyms denoting the absolute / unchanging opposite:

- constant opposite antonyms, naming denotations, characterized by the stability of entities opposite to each other (tirelessly - “tinim bilmay ishlamoq” and idly - “bekor yurmoq”; oranges sour - “uchishga noqulay ob-havo” and oranges sweet - “uchishga qulay ob-havo”);

- dynamically opposite antonyms, naming denotations with a reverse direction to each other and denoting a changing degree of opposition (getting out of strength - “charchagan” and gaining strength - “soga’ygan”);

2) antonyms denoting relative opposites: (as lowered into the water - “mayus, hafa” and in seventh heaven - “o’zida yo’q hursand”; golden parachute - “katta pul to’lamoq” and tin parachute - “oz pul to’lamoq”).

Despite highlighting the similarity of form as a formal criterion of antonymy, we note that in addition to verbal and phraseological oppositions, there are oppositions "word - phraseological unit". Opposed linguistic units in such oppositions differ in structure, shades of meanings and stylistic coloring. So, in the opposition e-mail - “elektron pochta” and snail mail - “oddiy pochta”, the first member is a complex abbreviated lexeme, neutral in style, the second member is characterized by imagery and indicates the slow pace of regular mail, compared with the speed of a crawling snail.

Among the reasons for the opposition of lexical and phraseological antonyms is the absence in the language of a word that would form such a contrast of meanings, and the speaker's desire for expressiveness, influencing interlocutors [3, p. 125].

CONCLUSION

The conducted research makes it possible to single out the following main criteria of antonymy: the presence of a homogeneous semantic structure and a differential component in opposing phraseological units; the presence of ultimate negation in the semantic structure, providing the opposite of the meanings of phraseological units; the identity of lexico-semantic and syntactic compatibility. A comparison of phraseological units of unrelated English and Uzbek languages revealed many common features, which allows us to assert that antonymy is a universal phenomenon, and it is unlawful to regard phraseological units as nationally determined.

LITERATURE:

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